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A STUDY ON THE CONSUMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS MOBILE BANKING SERVICES OF STATE BANK OF INDIA- WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DHARAMSHALA

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ABSTRACT

The banking industry and its customers have benefited greatly from recent telecommunications innovations. One such innovation is mobile banking, which allows customers to communicate with banks via cell phones and receive services like account information, fund transfers, short message services, check book issuance, and more. Mobile banking is a significant and developing method of carrying out financial operations. Currently, practically every bank in the globe offers "Mobile Banking" services to its customers. This research aims to investigate the Preference level of customers for Mobile Banking Services and the satisfaction level of customers towards Mobile Banking Services of SBI. This study is conducted in Dharamshala and customers using Mobile-banking service in State Bank of India (SBI). The present study has been collected from primary data on the basis of issue questionnaire, the sample size for study was only 81 mobile banking users of SBI.

Keywords: Mobile Banking, Customers Satisfaction and Preference level for adoption M-Banking

INTRODUCTION

In India, traditional banking through branches remains the most common method of conducting financial transactions; nevertheless, the use of information and communications technology (ICT) is causing significant changes in commercial banks. To meet the needs of its customers, the banking sector in India has developed a number of financial restructurings that would cause a transition from all conventional banking methods to digitalized banking services. A number of commercial banks have incorporated mobile banking through the use of ICT technology, allowing their customers to access dynamic retail banking transactions at any time and from any location in addition to basic service information. The delivery and utilization of banking and financial services using mobile telecommunications equipment is referred to as "Mobile Banking". The range of services supplied may include tools for managing accounts, conducting money transfers, and accessing personal data.

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Meaning of Mobile Banking and Mobile Banking Services:

The Federal Reserve survey defines mobile banking as “using a mobile phone to access your bank account, credit card account, or other financial account. Mobile banking can be done either by accessing your bank’s web page through the web browser on your mobile phone, via text messaging, or by using an application downloaded to your mobile phone.”

According to TRAI, mobile banking involves the use of mobile phones for banking transactions like fund transfer, balance check, etc. As per the extant guidelines of RBI, banks that are licensed, supervised and have a physical presence in India, are permitted to offer mobile banking services. Mobile Banking policies in India aim to enable funds transfer from an account in any bank to any other account in the same or any other bank (interoperability) on a real time basis irrespective of the mobile network the customer has subscribed to (TRAI, 2013). The Mobile phone plays a very important role in the development of mobile commerce and mobile banking.

People always carry a mobile phone, and services that go beyond voice and text messaging are becoming increasingly popular worldwide. The primary advantage of mobile banking over internet banking is that it allows customers to access their banks from anywhere by enabling "Anywhere Banking," which eliminates the requirement for a computer terminal. Now, they may do so while on the go—when traveling, waiting for their orders to be processed at a restaurant, or while they're waiting for their bus to get to work.

Mobile banking are supported by these services

- a) Account balance inquiry
- b) Cheque status inquiry
- c) Account statement inquiry
- d) Fund transfer between Accounts
- e) Cheque book requests
- f) Credit/debit alerts
- g) Minimum balance alerts
- h) Bill payment alerts
- i) Recent transaction literacy
- j) Bill payment

Mobile banking's array of services has demonstrated a path to the top of the banking industry's pyramid in the era of globalization and digitization. This medium has become a platform for providing customers with banking services due to its rapid user growth and increased network penetration. Customers are gravitating toward mobile banking in increasing numbers because they are pleased with the steps banks have made to secure these transactions. Carrying cash is no longer a concern with mobile banking. Numerous individuals can utilize and carry mobile phones everywhere.

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Mobile Banking & State Bank of India

State bank of India is an Indian Multinational Public sector bank and financial services statutory body. SBI is the 49th largest bank in the world by total assets and ranked 221st in the Fortune Global 500 List of the world's biggest corporations of 2020, being the only Indian bank in the list. It is also the fifth largest employer in India with nearly 250,000 employees. SBI became the third lender (after HDFC Bank and ICICI Bank) and seventh Indian company to cross the Rs5 trillion market capitalization on the Indian stock exchanges for the first time.

SBI is taking a leading role in the field of mobile banking in India. In this case, SBI is the only bank which spreads the financial literacy norms through mobile even in rural areas also, since it strengthens the Indian economy having largest number of branches all over India. State Bank of India offers mobile banking to its users via State Bank Anywhere (earlier it was SBI Freedom), which enables its customers to enjoy anytime, anywhere banking. The Mobile Banking Service provided by SBI can be used either via an Application/WAP (Wireless Application Protocol), SMS, or via USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data). Apart from the traditional mobile banking services SBI provides mobile banking through various mobile apps because SBI has the largest bouquet of apps amongst any Indian Bank. The app contains SBI Quick, Samadhan, mCash, OTP Secure, No Queue, State Bank Buddy, SBI YONO Lite etc. it has its own SBI Appkart App for all the apps.

Mobile Banking Services provided by State Bank of India:

1. Mobile Banking Service over Application/ Wireless Application Protocol (WAP)
2. Mobile Banking Service over SMS
3. Mobile Banking Service over USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data)

SBI Bank's Mobile Banking department is the largest alternate channel in volumes. It handles various critical customer-facing mobile applications/Services like UPI, Yono Lite SBI, Yono Business, SBI Quick, and SBI Secure OTP. The above apps enjoy an excellent reputation among customers and are known for their ease of use and outstanding user experience. Yono Lite has a total user base of 1.92 crore as of 31.03.2022. SBI Quick has a total user base of 2.99 crore as of Mar 22. Following developments have been done in SBI Quick mobile banking app. Thus, mobile banking is a cost effective method and banks offer such services at lesser cost so that all customers get access to it.

Review of Literature:

1. **Rejikumar G, Sudharani Ravindran D (2012)** the purpose of the paper to investigate the factors influencing the decisions of early adopters of mobile banking services. The study demonstrated that customers are satisfied with the quality framework of the services after selecting new technology. **Amit P.Wadhe, ShamraoGhodke (2013)**, this paper aims to investigate Pune city residents' perceptions and levels of consumer awareness regarding mobile banking. The researcher investigates the elements that

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contribute to significant consumers using mobile banking. Factor analysis, chi-square testing, and cross-tabulation were performed using SPSS software. Out of the 21 original elements, including the utility of mobile banking, its simplicity of use, consumer knowledge of mobile banking, and trust in banks, seven factors were retrieved as a result of factor analysis. **Simplice A.Asongu , Nicholas M Odhiambo (2017)** A study that enquire into the relationship between mobile banking & inclusive development that includes quality of growth , in equality and poverty. The conclusion that can be drawn out is that mobile banking application will play a supreme role in responding to the problems of deficient growth, inequality & poverty of the developing countries. **Sharma, S.K. and Sharma, M.,(2019)**,this study was conducted to understand users' actual usage of m-banking .The research model was tested and validated using data collected by survey from 227 Omani residents. This study employed a two-staged analytical approach by combining structural equation modeling and neural network analysis. On the basis of research, they concluded that service quality and trust are the key determinants influencing satisfaction and intention to use and in turn influence the actual usage of the mobile banking. **Sonia Bhatt (2020)**, the study indicates that Indian customers are willing to embrace mobile banking to a greater extent if it appears to be more dependable and trustworthy. Customers wouldn't be entirely motivated to use these solutions if there wasn't a reasonable degree of confidence. Several research works have elucidated the importance of trust, which in turn raises users' motivation to use these new technologies. **Geebren Ahmed, Jabbar Abdul and Luo Ming (2021)** in their paper examines the role of customer satisfaction in mobile banking services, specifically in a developing country. They used structural equation modeling with partial least squares (PLS-SEM) to analyze the data of 659 responses It investigates the impact of trust on customer satisfaction and finds that trust mediates the relationships between service quality, structural assurance, system quality, information quality, and task characteristics. **Chindengwike, J., (2022)** examines the contribution of mobile banking informational service on customer satisfaction in Tanzanian commercial banks. It concludes that mobile banking enhances customer satisfaction and recommends efforts to enhance mobile banking technology. **Huseynli Nigar and Huseynli Bahman (2023)** in their paper examine the relationship between customer experience and satisfaction, usage intention and brand loyalty in the context of mobile banking. The findings demonstrate that mobile banking usage intention and customer satisfaction affect loyalty to the bank brand, and customer satisfaction influences mobile banking usage intention.

Objectives of the Study:

- To determine the customer preference towards mobile banking services of SBI
- To examine the satisfaction level of customers towards Mobile Banking services of SBI

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

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The data for the survey was collected from the customers of SBI Mobile banking users of Dharamshala. A well-structured questionnaire served as the primary source. 81 samples were taken from the customers of SBI for the study with the help of random sampling method. Level of significance = 5% or 0.05. To test the hypotheses, SPSS package has been used to calculate the test statistics of analysis of variance.

Hypothesis:

The study is based on the following hypotheses:

- **H₀₁**: There is no significant impact of Demographic Variables (Annual income and Occupation) and customer satisfaction from SBI Mobile banking Services.
- **H₀₂**: There is no significant impact of Demographic Variables (Annual income and Occupation) and customer Preference for adoption of SBI mobile banking Services

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table: 1.1 GENDER WISE CLASSIFICATION

Gender	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents	Mean
Female	45	55.6	1.44
Male	36	44.4	
Total	81	100.0	

Source: Primary data

It is evident from the Table 1.1 that out of total respondents, 44.4% of respondents were male and 55.6% of respondents were female. Therefore, it concluded that a majority of the respondents were female.

Table: 1.2 AGE WISE CLASSIFICATION

Age	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents	Mean
18-35	70	86.4	1.16
36-50	9	11.1	
Above 50	2	2.5	
Total	81	100.0	

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 86.4% of the respondents were in the age group of 18-35 years, 11.1% of respondents were in the age of 36-50 years, 1% of the respondent was in the age group of below 50 years.

Therefore, it indicated that a majority of the respondents belonged to the age group of 18-35 years.

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TABLE NO 1.3: MARTIAL WISE CLASSIFICATION

Martial	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents	Mean
Unmarried	52	64.2	1.36
Married	29	35.8	
Total	81	100.0	

Source: Primary data

It is evident from the Table 1.3 that out of total respondents, 64.4% of respondents were Unmarried and 35.8% of respondents were married. Therefore, it concluded that a majority of the respondents were Unmarried.

TABLE NO 1.4: OCCUPATION WISE CLASSIFICATION

Occupation	Frequency of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents	Mean
Public undertaking	26	32.1	2.32
Private undertaking	10	12.3	
Self employed	38	46.9	
Professional	7	8.6	
Total	81	100.0	

Source: Primary data

The above table displays that 32.1% of the respondents were public employees, 12.3% of the respondents were private employees, 46.9 % of the respondents were self-employed and 8.6% of the respondents were professional.

Therefore, it indicated that a majority of the respondents were self-employed.

TABLE NO 1.5: ANNUAL INCOME WISE CLASSIFICATION:

Annual Income	Frequency of Respondent	Percentage of Respondent	Mean
Upto Rs2.5 lac	47	58.0	1.73
Rs 2.5 to Rs.5 lac	12	14.8	
Rs 5 to Rs. 10 Lac	19	23.5	
Above 10 lakh	3	3.7	
Total	81	100.0	

Source: Primary data

The above table gives a clear vision that 58.0 % of the respondents' annual income was upto Rs 2.5 lac, 14.8% of the respondents' annual income between Rs 2.5 lac to Rs 5 lac, 23.5% of the respondents' annual income between Rs 5 lac to Rs 10 lac and 3.7% of the respondents' annual income was above Rs 10 lac. The result revealed that a majority of the respondents' monthly income upto Rs. 2.5 lac.

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TABLE NO 1.6: QUALIFICATION WISE CLASSIFICATION

Qualification	Frequency of Respondent	Percentage of Respondent	Mean
Under Graduate	22	27.2	2.43
Graduate	13	16	
Post Graduate	44	54.3	
Technical Diploma	2	2.5	
Total	81	100	

Source: Primary data

The above table displays that 27.2 % of the respondents were under-Graduate, 16 % of the respondents were Graduate, 54.3 % of the respondents were post-Graduate and 2.5 % of the respondents were technical diploma holder.

Therefore, it indicated that a majority of the respondents were Post-Graduate.

Customer demographic variable (Occupation and Annual income) and Customer Satisfaction from Mobile Banking Services:

HYPOTHESIS:

Level of significance = 5% or 0.05

H_{01} : There is no significant impact of Demographic Variables (Annual income and Occupation) and customer satisfaction from SBI Mobile banking Services.

Table 1.7: ANOVA (Demographic Variables (Annual income and Occupation) and customer satisfaction

Statements (Satisfaction level)	H_{01} :Demographic variable: Occupation		Hypothesis	H_{01} :Demographic variable: Annual Income		Hypothesis (0.05)
	F	Sig.		F	Sig.	
1) Mobile banking app is very easy to understand and navigate	7.127	.000	significant	2.141	.102	Not significant
2) Provide security for each transaction while using M-Banking App.	6.140	.001	Significant	2.783	.046	significant
3) It is easy to make transfer Funds	6.675	.000	Significant	2.588	.059	significant
4) The chances of carelessness of third-party or banks related to loss of my personal information is nil.	6.594	.001	significant	1.704	.173	Not significant.

Source: Primary data

Table 1.7 show the Impact of demographic variables (H_{01} : There is no significant impact of demographic variable (i.e Occupation and Annual Income) of Customers and customer satisfaction from M-banking services. The result based on the demographic variable i.e

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Occupation found that overall P- value is less than 0.05. Null hypothesis is rejected. So we can say that there is significant relation between occupation and customer satisfaction towards M-Banking.

When we compare with annual income, we found that P-value is significant for security for transaction and funds transfer but not significant for easy to understand and navigate and for loss of personal information is nil.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of Demographic Variables (Annual income and Occupation) and customer Preference for adoption of SBI mobile banking Services

Table : 1.8 ANOVA (Demographic Variables (Annual income and Occupation) and Customer Preference

Statements	H ₀₂ :Demographic variable: Occupation		Hypothesis (0.05)	H ₀₂ :Demographic variable: Annual Income		Hypothesis (0.05)
	F	Sig.		F	Sig.	
	1) Saving of time	8.074		.000	Significant	
2) No need to visit the bank	5.994	.001	Significant	2.519	.064	Not significant
3) Customer Friendly	7.935	.000	Significant	1.807	.153	Not significant
4) Faster/ 24*7 transaction	8.002	.000	Significant	2.748	.049	significant
5) Language of Mobile Banking App is easy to operate	7.292	.000	Significant	2.266	.087	Not significant

Source: Primary data

In table 1.8, the result based on the demographic variable i.e Occupation found that overall P-value is less than 0.05. Null hypothesis is rejected. So we can say that there is significant relation between occupation and customer preference for adoption of M-Banking services of SBI. When we compare with annual income, we found that P- value is significant for faster/24*7 transaction services of mobile banking but for the rest of the statements P-value is greater than 0.05. So, Null hypothesis is accepted.

Summary of Findings:

- A majority (55.6%) of the respondents were female.
- A majority (86.4%) of the respondents belonged to the age group of 18-35 years.
- A majority (64.4%) of the respondents were unmarried.
- A majority (46.9%) of the respondents were self-employed
- A majority (58%) of the respondents' monthly income upto Rs. 2.5 lac.
- A majority (54.3%) of the respondents were Post-Graduate.

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- There is significant impact of customer occupation and customer satisfaction towards M-Banking.
- P-value is significant for security for transaction and funds transfer but not significant for easy to understand and navigate and for loss of personal information is nil when compare with Customer annual income.
- There is significant relation between Customer occupation and customer preference for adoption of M-Banking services of SBI.
- There is no significant impact of customer occupation and customer preference for adoption of M-Banking services of SBI except for faster/24*7 transaction services of mobile banking

Conclusion:

The study has analyzed the customer satisfaction as well as Preference level for adoption of mobile banking services for SBI. Mobile banking has numerous advantages and it brings out a number of customers to this service. From the above analysis, it was concluded that there is significant impact of demographic variable (i.e occupation and annual income) and Customer satisfaction towards mobile banking services of SBI. Majority of the customers were positively opinioned that mobile banking menu is very easy to understand and navigate, Provide security for each transaction, easy to make transfer of Funds and chances of carelessness of third-party or banks related to loss of my personal information is nil. We also analysed that there is significant impact of demographic variable (i.e occupation) and Customer preference for adoption of mobile banking services of SBI. As mobile banking help in saving their time , Customer Friendly, Faster/ 24*7 transaction and Language of Mobile Banking App is easy to operate but there is no significant impact of customer annual income and customer preference for adoption of Mobile banking services. The study is concerted on a particular location and hence the result may vary with locality and the demography of the people. The relatively small size of the sample limits generality of the outcome of the study.

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